

Research Article

Effects of Seedlings Transplanting Time on The Growth And Yield of Onion at Different AEZs

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Abstract : This work was conducted during the winter season of 2017-2018 to determine the appropriate seedlings transplanting time at two AEZs on the yield and quality of onion bulbs (BARI Piaz-1). There were six levels of seedlings planting time such as T_1 : 15 November, T_2 : 30 November, T_3 : 15 December, T_4 : 30 December, T_5 : 15 January and T_6 : 30 January and two Agro-ecological zones (AEZs) such as L_1 : Bogura (AEZ-4) and L_2 : Lalmonirhat (AEZ-2) in the experiment. The field trial was placed at the experimental farms of Spices Research Centre, Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute (BARI), Bogura and Spices Research Sub-Centre, BARI, Lalmonirhat. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design of factorial concept with three replications. The results revealed that seedlings transplanting times, AEZs and their combined effects had significant effect on the parameters studied with minor exception. The values for plant growth, onset of bulbing, incidence of bolting, maturity date, splitting & bolter bulbs and dry matter content of leaves were gradually decreased with the passage of transplanting time. Longer cold period facilitated for increasing of bolting at earlier stages of transplanting. But yield attributes and yield were increased up to the third transplanting time. After that it was decreased. However, due to inferior incidence of bolting, transplanting on 30 December exhibited the best performance for producing quality bulbs. Because of higher temperature and long day length, no bolting was occurred from 15-30 January. For the same reasons, transplanting seedling on 15-30 January gave poor yield of onion. Onion bulbs bolted bear hard centers that deteriorates quality and also decreases the market value of that bulb. The higher values of plant growth, onset of bulbing, incidence of

bolting, splitting & bolter bulbs were obtained from Lalmonirhat due to longer cold period prevailing in Lalmonirhat. Hence, considering the incidence of bolting, Bogura performed better for the yield attributes, yield and quality of onion. The combined effect of 30 December and Bogura gave the best quality of yield attributes and yield of onion. Differences in weather conditions between onion growing locations affect bulb quality. The experiment may be repeated at more AEZs to confirm the consistent results.

Keywords : *Agro-ecological zones (AEZs), Seedling Transplanting Time, BARI Piaz-1, Bulb, Bolting.*

Introduction

The enhancement of onion production is related to different growth factors. It depends on location of production, variety, nutrient management, agronomic practices like planting time, plant spacing etc. The use of appropriate agronomic practices has an undoubted contribution to increase quantity of quality yield of the crop. The optimum level of planting time of the crop varies with environment. Temperature controls the development and the performance of the onion plant in all its growth phases, as described by Coolong and Randle (2003). According to Shanmugasundaram and Kalb (2001), onion seedlings grow the best at temperatures between 20 and 25°C. For optimum vegetative growth before bulbing a temperature of between 18 and 22°C is needed. However, plants are still grown at temperatures as low as 10 and as high as 27°C (Comrie, 1997). From bulb initiation up to harvesting, higher temperatures between 25 and 28°C are required. Onions reacts to day length (photoperiod) for bulb initiation and the leaves of the plant are the photoperiodic stimulus receptor (Okporie and Ekpe, 2008). The photoperiodic stimulus favours carbohydrate accumulation exported from the leaf blade to the leaf sheath (Mattananda and Fordham, 1999), causing the sheaths of the leaves to thicken and enlarge. These thickened leaf sheaths will develop into a storage organ, the bulb. Short day onion cultivars require a day length of 11-12 hours for bulb formation (Wiles, 1989). Cool conditions are usually required during the first part of the season, when the plants start to form bulbs. Warm and dry conditions during the harvesting promote the rapid drying of the leaves, causing the neck of the bulb to dry off quickly that will prevent moisture loss from the bulb and maintaining the firmness of the bulb. With warm weather and bright days, onions bulb at shorter day length than when the days are cool and over cast (Hamasaki *et al.*, 1999). Vegetative growth, bulb development and maturity of onion vary from location to location, since these parameters are largely influenced by the prevailing climatic conditions (temperature, relative humidity, photoperiod, wind velocity, soil type and nutrition) at particular location in a given season, as noted by Heydecker (1972). In Bangladesh, onion is traditionally transplanted on different dates of December-January. But

onion plants, with some of the dates, show many flower stalks and split bulbs. While onions, with some of the dates, are harvested in early shower. Both of the stated conditions limit quality of onion bulbs. Determining an appropriate seedlings transplanting time is one of the most important requirements of farming planning to realize maximum yield with an optimum quality (Ezueh, 1982). It is also very difficult to advise the general recommendation that can be applicable to the different agro ecological zones (UAAE, 2001). Differences in weather conditions as well as the agricultural practices among onion growing locations might affect bulb quality. The situation deserves increasingly important to adjust seedlings transplanting time of onion for getting targeted achievements as per agro- ecological zones (AEZs).

Therefore, the present work was initiated to assess the seedlings transplanting times on the growth, development, quality, maturity and yield of onion with the variety BARI Piaz-1 as per AEZs.

Materials and Methods

A field trial was carried out during the winter season of 2017-2018 to explore the effects of the two AEZs (L₁ :Bogura, AEZ-04 and L₂:Lalmonirhat, AEZ-02) and six transplanting times (T₁:November 15, T₂:November 30, T₃:December 15, T₄:December 30, T₅:January 15 and T₆:January 30) of onion on the growth, development, quality, maturity and yield of onion. The experiment was set at two stations of Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute (BARI): (a) Spices Research Centre, Shibganj, Bogura and (b) Spices Research Sub-Centre, Lalmonirhat. The parameters under investigation were on plant height, number of leaves per plant, onset of bulbing, neck size, percent of bolting, maturity date, diameter of bulb, individual bulb weight, percent of split & bolter bulbs, dry matter of bulbs, dry matter of leaves, total soluble solid and yield of onion. The trial was laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design of factorial arrangement with three replications. The size of plot was 2.5 m x 1.2 m which was calculated in 0.003 ha. The experimental field was fertilized with 10 t well-decomposed cowdung, 120 kg N, 50 kg P, 85 kg K and 50 kg S per hectare. Nitrogen, phosphate, potash and sulphur were supplied in the form of Urea, TSP, MP and Gypsum, respectively. The entire quantity of cowdung, P, K,S and one third of N were applied as basal dose during land preparation. The remaining N was used as top dress in two equal splits at 20 and 30 days after seedlings transplanting. Seeds of BARI Piaz-1 were sown at 45 days before seedlings transplanting. The first sowing was done on October 01, 2017. However, the seedlings were transplanted in flat bed having spacing of 15 cm

x 10 cm at two locations on different dates as per treatments designed. Intercultural operations such as irrigation, weeding out and pest management were carried out similarly in all treatments. There was no serious incidence of diseases and pests. Ten plants were randomly selected from each plot for data recoding. Soil samples were randomly collected at 0-30 cm soil depth for physical and chemical analysis before the commencement of the experiment. The physical and chemical characteristics of experimental soils from two locations were presented in Table 1. While monthly periodical records of average air temperature for both locations during 2017-18 was presented graphically (Fig. 1). While total rainfall and relative humidity for two AEZs during 2017-18 were shown in Table 2. Simple randomization of each plot was done to select ten plants and plant parameters cited above were recorded. Plant height and number of leaves were recorded at 30 and 60 days after seedling transplanting. But average plant height and number of leaves were presented in Table 3, Table 4 and Table 5. Bulbs were harvested at maturity when the pseudostem becomes flaccid and unable to support the leaf blades (Brewster, 1990^a). As per the experiment, November 15-March 4, November 30-March 10, December 15-March 19, December 30-March 25, January 15-April 3 and January 30-April 10 fell in first, second, third, fourth, fifth and sixth stage, respectively. The leaves of harvested onion were removed at seven days after curing by cutting 8-10 cm above the bulb (Brewster, 1990^c). Weight of bulbs was recorded after curing. Observations in respect of economic and biological yield per plant on dry weight basis in oven at 65 °C for 24 h (Singh *et al.*, 1998) were determined. Onset of bulbing was calculated in days when the ratio of maximum bulb diameter to minimum pseudostem diameter exceeds 2:1 (Steer, 1980)). The recorded data were analyzed statistically and the means were compared by LSD method for AEZs and DMRT method for transplanting time & combined effects (Gomez and Gomez, 1984).

Table 1. Physical and chemical characteristics of initial soil at experimental plots in 2017-2018

Locations	Soil texture	Soil pH	OM (%)	K	Ca	Mg	Total N	P	S	B	Zn	Fe	Cu	Mn
				meq/100 g				µg/g soil						
Lalmonirhat	Sandy loam	5.82	1.24	0.23	2.61	0.73	0.062	72.76	44.64	0.04	0.55	84.97	2.16	40.40
Bogura	Sandy loam	5.6	1.02	0.33	2.4	0.93	0.06	15.2	8.3	0.13	1.25	-	0.12	-
Critical level			-	0.12	2.0	0.5	0.12	7.0	10.0	0.2	0.6	4.0	0.2	1.0

Fig. 1. Periodical records of average air temperature at experimental plots in 2017-2018 (from 1-10, 11-20 and 21-last day of the month represent the 1st, 2nd and 3rd part of the month, respectively)

Table 2. Periodical records of average relative humidity and rainfall at experimental plots in 2017-2018

Month	Period	Bogura		Lalmonirhat	
		Relative humidity (%)	Total rainfall (mm)	Relative humidity (%)	Total rainfall (mm)
October 2017	01-10	94.20	5.9	96.00	14.65
	11-20	92.80	3.5	94.00	1.00
	21-31	99.40	0.21	96.18	133.00
November 2017	01-10	94.00	0	95.20	0
	11-20	92.90	0.20	92.80	0.20
	21-30	87.90	0	94.30	0.20
December 2017	01-10	91.60	1.5	96.80	0
	11-20	94.70	0	97.80	0
	21-31	99.60	0	98.55	0
January 2018	01-10	94.80	0	99.40	0
	11-20	97.00	0	100.00	0
	21-31	99.50	0	98.81	0
February 2018	01-10	89.80	0	97.10	0
	11-20	88.30	0	97.70	0
	21-28	73.30	0.70	92.63	0
March 2018	01-10	84.20	0	91.70	0
	11-20	84.70	0	86.20	0
	21-31	96.20	0	88.72	13.40
April 2018	01-10	87.50	23.6	91.30	30.40
	11-20	81.80	0.80	92.60	78.40
	21-30	89.20	7.9	92.80	43.40

Effect of seedlings transplanting times

Plant growth: Significant effect was found among the levels of seedlings transplanting time for the plant growth attributes studied (Table 3). Very early transplanting (T₁) of seedlings on November 15 had the maximum plant height (53.36 cm), number of leaves per plant (8.80), neck

size (15.22 mm), incidence of bolting (76.56%), fresh weight of flower stalks per plot (3.41 kg) which was followed by T₂ (November 30). Generally, long cold receiving onion plants produce more bolting compared to the short one. More or less, at both the AEZs temperature (Fig. 1) and day length were increased with the passage of seedling transplanting time. The maximum values for plant growth traits from earlier transplanting might be due to longer cold period prevailing. Singh and Korla (1981) transplanted onion seedlings at fortnightly intervals starting from November 16 to December 31 and concluded that delay in transplanting caused decreased in number of leaves. Incidences of bolting occurred at four consecutive transplanting dates from T₁-T₄ were 76.56, 59.92, 30.16 and 2.57%, respectively. This phenomenon happened due to low temperature but comparatively longer low temperature was prevailing at earlier transplanting than later one. Thicker neck from earlier transplanting might have occurred due to emerging flowering stalks and also higher number of leaves. Percent of bolting was increased with low temperature, as reported by Yamasaki and Miura (1995). At low temperature plants catch sufficient leaves resulting in the sexual phase (Brewster, 1994). Prolong low temperature increases bolting and also the speed of the phenomenon (Tarpaga *et al.*, 2011). While late transplanting (T₅ and T₆) produced the minimum values of these growth traits. However, the lowest values of plant height (39.50 cm), number of leaves per plant (6.38), neck size (10.74 mm), incidence of bolting (0%) were noted by T₆ (January 30). And these lowest values were followed by T₅ (January 15). The shortest plant, the lowest number of leaves per plant, neck size, onset of bulbing and no incidence of flowering stalks obtained from January 15-30 transplanting might be due to higher temperature prevailing (Fig. 1) at longer day that reduced growth of onion plant. A number of researchers (Austin, 1972 and Wright and Sobeih, 1986) stated that higher temperature decreases leaf number and longer the day, sooner the plant growth ceases. Temperature and photoperiod are the major ecological factors influencing onion growth and development (Rabinowitch, 1985) as those control the onion plant in all phases (Coolong and Randle, 2003). The delay in sowing adversely influences the growth and development of plants due to shortened growth period with high temperature (Mohamedali and Nourai, 1988). While Khan and Shanmugasundaram (2013) stated that at the same planting time, bolting markedly reduced number of leaves. No flowering stalks at fifth and sixth stages of transplanting were observed due to higher temperature prevailing during growing period. Delay transplanting reduced the percent of bolting than that of early transplanting, as registered by Bhamburkar *et*

al., (1986). Bolting was more prevalent in crops that emerged before the period of lowest temperatures in winter and hence, it appears that the plants needed to attain a critical size before they were receptive to the bolting stimulus (Voss, 1979). High temperature is unfavourable for flowering in onion, as reported by Nikus and Mulugeta (2010). Abu-Rayyan and Abu-Irmaileh (2004) reported that onion required cool weather during inflorescence initiation. Longer cold exposure results in a greater percent of bolting in onion (Kelley and Granberry, 2000). Onion bulbs bolted bear hard centres that deteriorates quality and also decreases the market value of that bulb. The hard centre is explained by Adsul *et al.* (2009) as formation of cellulosic, woody, non-edible structure in the centre of onion.

Table 3. Effects of seedlings transplanting times on growth, development, maturity and yield of onion

Seedlings transplanting times	Plant height (cm)	No. leaves per plant	Onset of bulbing (days)	Neck size (mm)	Bolting (%)	Fresh wt. of flower stalks /plot (kg)	Maturity date (days)
T ₁ :Nov. 15	53.36a	8.80a	69.05a	15.22a	76.56a	3.41a	105.33a
T ₂ :Nov. 30	51.77ab	8.35ab	62.07b	14.03a b	59.92b	2.44b	98.17b
T ₃ :Dec. 15	49.70b	7.78bc	59.44c	13.54b	30.16c	1.23c	92.33c
T ₄ :Dec. 30	46.74c	7.47c	55.27d	12.27c	2.57d	0.21d	86.43d
T ₅ :Jan. 15	43.20d	7.02cd	46.17e	10.98d	0.00d	0.00e	77.43e
T ₆ :Jan. 30	39.50e	6.38d	40.93f	10.74d	0.00d	0.00e	68.50f
CV%	4.66	8.78	3.81	5.36	7.96	8.25	3.66
Level of significance	**	**	**	**	**	**	**

Contd. Table 3

Seedlings transplanting times	Bulb diameter (cm)	Individual bulb weight (g)	Split & bolter bulbs (%)	Dry matter of bulbs (%)	Dry matter of leaves (%)	TSS (^o brix)	Yield/ ha (t)
T ₁ :Nov. 15	3.83b	24.52b	87.96a	17.22a	16.03a	16.34a	17.09ab
T ₂ :Nov. 30	3.96 ab	24.96ab	70.09b	17.25a	15.63a	16.58a	17.55a
T ₃ :Dec. 15	4.11 a	25.56a	41.71c	17.33a	15.37a	16.81a	17.98a
T ₄ :Dec. 30	3.44c	24.49b	13.71d	17.48a	15.31a	16.88a	16.99b
T ₅ :Jan. 15	2.68d	12.61c	10.49e	14.15b	13.38b	13.30b	7.57c
T ₆ :Jan. 30	2.35e	10.95d	6.58f	12.40c	11.78c	11.97c	6.91c
CV%	6.14	6.20	5.32	3.34	5.05	4.67	6.36
Level of significance	**	**	**	**	**	**	**

** Significant at 1% level of significance

Bulb development: The date of seedlings transplanting showed the significant variation on onset of bulbing, bulb diameter, individual bulb weight, bolting & bolter bulbs, total soluble solid content (TSS) and dry matter of bulbs (Table 3). The onset of bulbing and the percent of split & bolter bulbs were decreased with the passage of transplanting time ranged from 69.05-40.93 days and 87.96-6.58%, respectively. The current findings corroborate the results of Hutton and Wilson (1986). The earlier sowing dates resulted in high proportion of bulbs that bolted and severely reduced marketable yield, as noted by Hutton and Wilson (1986). Adsul *et al.* (2009) stated that the stored edible materials of the bulbs were lost due to nuisance of bolting. The percent of the lowest splitting & bolter bulbs from late transplanting might be due to occurring no bolting in these treatments as higher temperature was prevailing (Fig. 1). The present findings are in agreement with reports of others workers. Higher temperature is more effective in accelerating bulbing (Steer, 1980). Long day length with high temperature promoted bulbing (Khan and Shanmugasundaram, 2003). Adsul *et al.* (2009) also noted that the environmental conditions influenced the percent of bolting. While the diameter of bulb, individual bulb weight and yield were increased up to third stage of transplanting time ranged from 3.83-4.11 cm, 24.52-25.56 g and 17.09-17.98 t/ha, respectively. The present result is not consistent with the finding of Hamasaki *et al.* (1999). They reported that the more leaves present, the larger bulb was obtained from the onion plant. But in the current experiment, the bulb weight and bulb size might be reduced due to production of flowering stalk. Khan and Shanmugasundaram (2013) stated that at same planting time, bolting markedly reduced bulb weight. The storage of photosynthate in onion bulb was hampered and was in turn utilized for flowering stalks ignition, which might be the reasons for smaller bulb size (Arvin and Banakar, 2002). Then the values of these traits were declined up to last stage of transplanting ranged from 3.44-2.35 cm, 24.49-10.95 g and 16.99-6.91 t/ha, respectively. Minimum bulb size and individual bulb weight from late transplanting seedlings were probably due to growing of late transplanted crops at higher temperature (Fig. 1). The findings are in line with the findings of Khan and Shanmugasundaram (2003). Bulb size and bulb weight were reduced markedly at long day length with high temperature, as described by Khan and Shanmugasundaram (2003). Bulb weight was affected by planting time (Hutton and Wilson, 1986 and Caruso *et al.*, 2014). Delay in transplanting reduced bulb weight (Singh and Korla, 1991 and Singh, 1993). Dry matter content and total soluble solid content were increased steadily from first transplanting to fourth one and ranged from 17.22-17.48% and 16.34-16.88

⁰brix, respectively. The TSS content of the bulbs from earlier transplanting seedlings might be reduced due to bearing profuse hard centres. Then the values of these attributes were reduced sharply because of occurring rainfall at the maturity stages of bulbs. Late transplanting also gave the lowest dry matter content of leaves which was also subjected to adverse weather condition (heavy rainfall) at maturity stage of bulbs (Table 2). The total soluble solids content (TSS) was positively correlated with dry matter content of bulbs (Lee *et al.*, 2012). While bulb size decreased as dry matter increased (Mallor *et al.*, 2011). The finding of Mallor *et al.* (2011) is contrasting with the present findings because profuse flowering stalks at earlier transplanting reduced the bulb size. The hard centres in the bulbs, which produce flowering stalks, deteriorate quality and also decrease the market value of those bulbs. Onion quality also was influenced by temperature and rainfall (Lee *et al.*, 2012). But for producing quality bulbs, the best transplanting time was the fourth one (December 30) as the maximum bulbs were bolters growing from first to third transplantings.

Maturity and yield: Different transplanting dates significantly affected maturity date and yield of onion (Table 3). Late transplanting significantly accelerated the maturity (77.43 and 68.50 days) at T₅ and T₆, respectively. It might be due to higher temperature prevailing at longer day in these treatments. The finding of the present study is in conformity with that of Austin (1972) who claimed that longer the day, sooner the leaf growth ceases and sooner the bulbs ripens. The time from commencement of bulb formation to bulb maturity is related to environmental conditions during that period only (Voss, 1979). Earlier transplanted plants had more leaves that made the necks thicker and hence, which might be delayed maturity. The time to maturity decreased as the sowing date was delayed (Hutton and Wilson, 1986). The highest yields (17.98, 17.55 t/ha) were observed from the third (T₃) & the second (T₂) transplanting, respectively followed by T₁ (17.09 t/ha). The maximum yields obtained from the first to third transplantings might be because of low temperature prevailing for long period (Fig. 1) as low temperature is favourable for bigger bulb development. Generally in spite of greater yield obtained from first three transplanting dates, the yield was increased steadily from first transplanting to third one. The flower stalks yield of 3.41-1.23 kg/plot (0.003 ha) i.e. 1.14 - 0.41 t/ha were found from first to third transplanting. While plants at the fourth transplanting exhibited the minimum flower stalks/plot (0.21 kg) i.e. 0.07 t/ha. Decreasing trend in yield from third to first stage of transplanting might be due to higher incidence of bolting. After the third stage of transplanting,

the yield was declined up to last stage of transplanting. But the yields were markedly reduced by delaying transplanting at T₅ and T₆ (7.57 and 6.91 t/ha), respectively. The reduced yields from late transplanting of seedlings might happen due to producing smaller bulbs by seedlings of late transplanting and due to higher temperature prevailing during growing period at late transplanting. Reduction in total yield was recorded at later sowing dates was caused by a reduction in average bulb size (Hutton and Wilson, 1986). Singh and Korla (1981) transplanted onion seedlings at fortnightly intervals starting from November 16 to December 31 and concluded that delay in transplanting caused decreased in yield. Hence, transplanting seedlings on December 30 (T₄) exhibited the best performance considering quality in respect of bolting, split & bolter bulbs, dry matter of bulbs and TSS content. Early transplanting produced profuse undesirable flowering stalks (bolting) and the bulbs containing flowering stalks bear hard centre. The hard centre of the bulb deteriorates quality and also decreases the market value of that bulb.

Effects of AEZs

Plant growth: The results inferred that plant growth parameters were significantly affected by AEZs (Table 4). The higher values of plant height (49.11 cm), number of leaves per plant (8.10), onset of bulbing (56.34 days), neck size (13.18 mm), incidence of bolting (29.63%) and fresh weight of flowers per plot (1.33 kg) were obtained from Lalmonirhat. The two AEZs also differed in their weather conditions (Fig. 1 & Table 2). Comparatively lower temperature was prevailed at Lalmonirhat: max. 19.72-33.00⁰C and min. 8.74-25.67⁰C. While higher temperature was prevailed at Bogura: max. 21.06-35.15⁰C and min. 9.10-26.33⁰C. So, the extended exposure of the crop to the low temperature for a prolonged period may lead to better vegetative, development and flowering traits. Thus, higher flowering stalks were obtained from Lalmonirhat than those of Bogura. The findings of present experiment are in accordance with those of previous workers. Abu-Rayyan and Abu-Irmaileh (2004) reported that onion required cool weather during inflorescence initiation. Longer cold exposure results in a greater percent of bolting in onion (Kelley and Granberry, 2000). Agro ecological zones (AEZs) have greatest influence on crop growth due to variabilities of weather and soil conditions (FAO, 1978). The zonation schemes have been used to identify limiting factors for crop growth (Williams *et al.*, 2008), to regionalize optimum crop management recommendations (Seppelt, 2000), to determine suitable locations for new crop production technologies (Araya *et al.*, 2010) and to analyze impacts of climate change on agriculture (Fischer *et al.*, 2005).

Table 4. Effects of AEZs on growth, development, maturity and yield of onion

AEZs	Plant height (cm)	No. leaves per plant	Onset of bulbing (days)	Neck size (mm)	Bolting (%)	Fresh wt. of flower stalks /plot (kg)	Maturity date (days)
L ₁ :Bogura	45.64	7.16	54.63	12.41	26.79	1.09	87.29
L ₂ :Lalmonirhat	49.11	8.10	56.34	13.18	29.63	1.33	88.78
LSD (0.05)	1.525	0.453	1.461	0.489	1.552	0.069	-
CV%	4.66	8.78	3.81	5.36	7.96	8.25	3.66
Level of significance	**	**	**	**	**	**	NS

Contd. Table 4

AEZs	Bulb diameter (cm)	Individual bulb weight (g)	Split & bolter bulbs (%)	Dry matter of bulbs (%)	Dry matter of leaves (%)	TSS (^o brix)	Yield/ ha (t)
L ₁ :Bogura	3.58	21.36	36.25	16.50	14.44	16.29	14.86
L ₂ :Lalmonirhat	3.20	19.67	40.59	15.44	14.74	14.34	13.16
LSD (0.05)	0.146	0.785	1.412	0.369	-	0.711	0.542
CV%	6.14	6.20	5.32	3.34	5.05	4.67	6.36
Level of significance	**	**	**	**	NS	*	**

** Significant at 1% level of significance, * Significant at 5% level of significance, NS Not significant

Bulb development: The effects of AEZs on all measured characters were significant except dry matter content of leaves studied (Table 4). Lalmonirhat exhibited higher split & bolter bulb (40.59%) than that of Bogura. It happened due to emerging higher flowering stalk at plants of Lalmonirhat receiving longer cold temperature (Fig. 1). Diameter of bulb (3.58 cm), individual bulb weight (21.36 g), dry matter content of bulb (16.50%), TSS content (16.29 ^obrix) and bulb yield (14.86 t/ha) were higher at Bogura. Lower bulb size from Lalmonirhat might be due to production of higher flowering stalks at Lalmonirhat. The finding of the present study is in conformity with those of other workers. The storage of photosynthate in onion bulb was hampered and was in turn utilized for flowering stalks ignition, which might be the reasons for smaller bulb size (Arvin and Banakar, 2002). Adsul *et al.* (2009) found regional influence on onion bulb size. The fresh weight and dry matter content of the bulbs were significantly affected by the location (Lee *et al.*, 2016). The diameters and the TSS contents were significantly different between transplanting location, also reported by Lee *et al.* (2016). Onions from

Lalmonirhat had both a lower fresh weight and a lower dry matter content, which might be caused by the weather conditions, such as prolonged lower temperature (Fig. 1) during growing season and the high precipitation in the late harvesting stage (Lee *et al.*, 2016). The maximum (30.40 mm) and minimum (3.60 mm) rainfall (Table 2) were occurred in Lalmonirhat and Bogura at the bulb maturity stages of fifth-sixth transplanting, respectively. In contrast, bulbs with a lower dry matter generally have a higher fresh weight of bulbs, a trend previously noted by Currah and Proctor (1990). The finding of present work does not support the finding of Currah and Proctor (1990). Because, in the present experiment, the storage of photosynthate in onion bulb was utilized for flowering stalks ignition, which might be the reasons for smaller bulb size (Arvin and Banakar, 2002).

Maturity and yield: The AEZs had a great influence on the yield of onion bulb but a little influence on maturity date (Table 4). Higher yield of onion bulb (14.86 t/ha) was obtained from Bogura than that of (13.16 t/ha) Lalmonirhat. The finding of the present study is in conformity with those of other workers. The storage of photosynthate in onion bulb was hampered and was in turn utilized for flowering stalks ignition, which might be the reasons for smaller bulb size (Arvin and Banakar, 2002) and hence, the yield obtained from Lalmonirhat was comparatively lower. Agro ecological zones (AEZs) have greatest influence on the yield due to variabilities of weather and soil conditions (FAO, 1978). The crop yield potential (Y_p) is location-specific because the Y_p is determined by weather, management, length of growing season and soil properties (FAO, 1996). The zonation schemes have been used to identify yield variability (Williams *et al.*, 2008), to compare yield trends (Gallup and Sachs, 2000), to determine suitable locations for new crop production technologies (Araya *et al.*, 2010) and to analyze impacts of climate change on agriculture (Fischer *et al.*, 2005).

Combined effects of seedlings transplanting times and AEZs

The combined effects of transplanting times and AEZs had significant effect on the attributes studied (Table 5). Transplanting seedlings on November 15 at Lalmonirhat demonstrated the maximum values of plant growth traits: plant height (54.93 cm), number of leaves (9.44), onset of bulbing (69.33 days), neck size (15.49 mm), incidence of bolting (78.12%) and fresh weight of flowering stalks per plot (3.82 kg). While the minimum values of plant height (38.03 cm), number of leaves (6.25), onset of bulbing (39.75 days) and neck size (10.51 mm) were recorded

at Bogura x January 30. No bolting was seen in Bogura and Lalmonirhat for the last two transplanting stages (January 15 and January 30). The maximum growth traits from Lalmonirhat x November 15 might be due to combined effects of receiving prolonged low temperature (Fig. 1). Minimum growth values from later transplanting stage might be due to prevailing higher temperature (Fig. 1) at the growth stages of later transplanting that reduced growth of onion plant. On the other hand, no incidence of flowering stalks was observed from January 15-30 transplanting at Lalmonirhat and Bogura. This phenomenon had happened due to wanting of prolonged low temperature at the growth stages of January 15-30 as higher temperature was prevailing (Fig. 1) at longer day. A number of researchers (Austin, 1972 and Wright and Sobeih, 1986) stated that higher temperature decreases leaf number and longer the day, sooner the plant growth ceases. Temperature and photoperiod are the major ecological factors influencing onion growth and development (Rabinowitch, 1985) as those control the onion plant in all phases (Coolong and Randle, 2003). The delay in sowing adversely influences the growth and development of plants due to shortened growth period with high temperature (Mohamedali and Nourai, 1988). Delay transplanting reduced the percent of bolting than that of early transplanting, as registered by Bhamburkar *et al.*, (1986). Bolting was more prevalent in crops that emerged before the period of lowest temperatures in winter, and, hence, it appears that the plants needed to attain a critical size before they were receptive to the bolting stimulus (Voss, 1979). High temperature is unfavourable for flowering in onion, as reported by Nikus and Mulugeta (2010). Abu-Rayyan and Abu-Irmaileh (2004) reported that onion required cool weather during inflorescence initiation. Longer cold exposure results in a greater percent of bolting in onion (Kelley and Granberry, 2000). Lalmonirhat x November 15 took long time (106 days) to get maturity of bulb which was insignificantly followed by Bogura x November 15 (104.66 days). While late transplanting at January 15-30 in both locations markedly reduced the maturity time ranging from 67.66-78.00 days. Temperature was higher at later stages of growing onion in both locations (Fig. 1) that facilitated the plants for ceasing growth stages of onions. The highest diameter of bulb (3.98, 4.12 & 4.25 cm), individual bulb weight (25.65, 26.01 & 26.70 g) and bulb yield (18.10, 18.53 and 18.96 t/ha) were noted from combined effects of Bogura x November 15, Bogura x November 30 and Bogura x December 15, respectively. The lowest diameter of bulb, individual bulb weight and yield of bulb were recorded from the combined effects of Lalmonirhat x January 30, Lalmonirhat x January 15, Bogura x January 30 and Bogura

x January 15. The combined effects of Bogura x December 30 produced comparatively higher yield (17.89 t/ha) than that of (17.00 t/ha) combined effects between Lalmonirhat and December 30. But the combined effects of Bogura x December 30 gave lower undesirable split & bolter bulb (12.08%) than that of (15.33%) of combined effects between Lalmonirhat and December 30. On the other hand, higher split & bolter bulb were recorded from the combined effects of Lalmonirhat x November 15 (90.30%), Bogura x November 15 (85.62%), Bogura x November 30 (70.40%), Lalmonirhat x November 30 (69.78%) Lalmonirhat x December 15 (46.71%) and Bogura x December 15 (36.71%). While the lowest values (4.62, 8.12 and 8.53%) for the same trait were recorded from the combined effects between Bogura x January 30, Bogura x January 15 and Lalmonirhat x January 30, respectively. However, the combined effects between Bogura and December 30 presented the highest dry matter content of bulb (17.99%) and TSS content of bulb (18.27 °brix). Hence, considering quality of bulb, the combined effects between Bogura and December 30 showed the best performance for production of onion.

Table 5. Combined effects of seedlings transplanting times and AEZs on growth, development, maturity and yield of onion

Seedlings transplanting time x AEZs		Plant height (cm)	No. of leaves/plant	Onset of bulb in g (days)	Neck size (mm)	Bolting (%)	Fresh wt. of flower stalks /plot (kg)	Maturity date (days)
L ₁	T ₁	51.78a-c	8.15b-d	68.77a	14.96ab	74.99a	2.99b	104.66a
	T ₂	49.60c	7.47c-f	61.07bc	13.40c	59.01b	2.41c	98.00b
	T ₃	48.22cd	7.22c-g	58.00cd	12.99d	24.56d	0.98e	91.33cd
	T ₄	44.88de	7.06d-g	54.87d	11.99e	2.15e	0.15fg	85.21e
	T ₅	41.35ef	6.81e-g	45.34ef	10.66fg	0.00e	0.00g	76.85f
	T ₆	38.03f	6.25g	39.75g	10.51g	0.00e	0.00g	67.66g
L ₂	T ₁	54.93a	9.44a	69.33a	15.49a	78.12a	3.82a	106.00a
	T ₂	53.94ab	9.22ab	63.06b	14.67ab	60.83b	2.47c	98.33b
	T ₃	51.17bc	8.33a-c	60.88bc	14.09b	35.83c	1.47d	93.33bc
	T ₄	48.60cd	7.88c-d	55.66d	12.55de	2.99e	0.27f	87.66dc
	T ₅	45.05de	7.22c-g	47.00e	11.30f	0.00e	0.00g	78.00f
	T ₆	40.97f	6.51fg	42.11fg	10.98fg	0.00e	0.00g	69.33g
CV%		4.66	8.78	3.81	5.36	7.96	8.25	3.66
Level of significance		*	*	*	*	**	**	*

Contd. Table 5

Seedlings transplanting time x AEZs	Bulb diameter (cm)	Individual bulb weight (g)	Split & bolter bulbs (%)	Dry matter of bulbs (%)	Dry matter of leaves (%)	TSS (⁰ brix)	Yield/ha (t)	
L ₁	T ₁	3.98a-c	25.65b	85.62b	17.79ab	16.29ab	17.81a	18.10ab
	T ₂	4.12ab	26.01ab	70.40c	17.81ab	15.65a	17.77a	18.53a
	T ₃	4.25a	26.70a	36.71e	17.85ab	15.04b	18.20a	18.96a
	T ₄	3.73c	25.55b	12.08f	17.99a	14.87bc	18.27a	17.89ab
	T ₅	2.89d	13.2c	8.12g	14.63d	12.99dc	13.62bc	8.08d
	T ₆	2.51e	11.02d	4.62h	12.92e	11.80e	12.08d	7.65de
L ₂	T ₁	3.68c	23.39bc	90.30a	16.65c	15.87ab	14.88b	16.08c
	T ₂	3.79bc	23.86bc	69.78c	16.70c	15.60ab	15.39b	16.58bc
	T ₃	3.97a-c	24.42bc	46.71d	16.81c	15.70ab	15.41b	17.00b
	T ₄	3.15d	23.45bc	15.33f	16.96bc	15.75ab	15.50b	16.02c
	T ₅	2.46e	12.00c	12.86f	13.67e	13.77cd	12.99c	7.05e
	T ₆	2.19f	10.88d	8.53g	11.88f	11.77e	11.87d	6.16f
CV%	6.14	6.20	6.20	5.32	3.34	5.05	4.67	
Level of significance	*	*	*	**	*	*	*	

** Significant at 1% level of significance, * Significant at 5% level of significance, T₁ : November 15, T₂: November 30, T₃: December 15, T₄: December 30, T₅: January 15 and T₆: January 30, L₁: Bogura, AEZ-4 and L₂: Lalmonirhat, AEZ-2

Conclusion

The effects of seedling transplanting time as per AEZs on the balance between quality and quantity of yield conclude that:

- I. The optimum time to transplant seedlings was the last week of December.
- II. Bogura showed better performance.
- III. Earlier transplanting of seedlings produced profuse undesirable flowering stalks (bolting) that decreased the quality of bulb.
- IV. Delayed transplanting of seedling markedly reduced the yield due to higher temperature & long day length and quality: dry matter and TSS content of bulbs due to early rainfall.
- V. The present results, however, need to be further confirmed by conducting trail on more AEZs such as Rajshahi, Faridpur, Cumilla, Mymensingh and so on before recommendation.

References

- Abu-Rayyan, A. M. and B. E. Abu-Irmaileh. 2004. Onion development and yield responses to manual cultivation, herbicides or colored mulches. *J. Veg. Crop Prod.*, 10:37-49.
- Adsul, G. G.; A. V. Dhake and R. M. Kothari. 2009. Short-day onion improvement program in India for producing dehydrated products. *Biotechnology of an Indian Journal*, 3(3):116-124.
- Araya, A.; S. D. Keesstra; and L. Stroosnijder. 2010. A new agro-climatic classification for crop suitability zoning in northern semi-arid Ethiopia. *Agric. Forest Meteorol.*, 150:1057-1064.
- Arvin, M. J. and M. H. Banakar. 2002. Effects of plant growth regulators on bolting and several traits of onion cv. Texas Early Grano. *J. Sci. Tech. Agri. Natural Resources*, 6(1):59-70.
- Bhamburkar, A. A.; J. M. Rajput; L. V. Kulwal; P. B. Kale; K. T. Sadawarle and P. P. Deshmukh. 1986. Bolting in onion as influenced by date of planting, nitrogen and cultivars. *P. K. V. Res. J.*, 10 (2):115-118.
- Brewster, J. L. 1994. Onions and Other Vegetables Alliums. CAB International, Wallingford, UK. P. 236.
- Caruso, G.; S. Conti; G. Villari; C. Borrelli; G. Melchionna; M. Minutolo; G. Russo and C. Amalfitano. 2014. Effects of transplanting time and plant density on yield, quality and antioxidant content of onion in southern Italy. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 166:111
- Coolong, T. W. and W. M. Randle. 2003. Silfur and nitrogen availability interact to affect the flavor biosynthetic pathway in onion. *J. Amer. Soc. Hort. Sci.*, 128:776-783.
- Coolong, T. W. and W.M. Randle. 2003. Temperature influences flavor intensity and quality in 'Granex 33' onion. *J. Amer. Soc. Hort. Sci.*, 128:176-181.
- Currah, L and F. J. Proctor. 1990. Onions in tropical regions. Bulletin No. 35. National Research Institute, Kent, UK.
- FAO. 1978. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. Report on the Agro-Ecological Zones Project. Vol. 1. Methodology and Results for Africa. Rome, Italy.
- FAO. 1996. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. Agro-Ecological Zoning Guidelines. Soil Resources, Management and Conservation Service. FAO Land and Water Development Division. FAO Soils Bulletin 76. Rome, Italy. 73 p.
- Fischer, G; M. Shah; F. N. Tubiello and H. V. Velhuizen. 2005. Socio-economic and climate change impacts on agriculture: an integrated assessment, 1990-2080. *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. Lond. B.*, 360:2067-2083.
- Gallup, J. L. and J. D. Sachs. 2000. Agriculture, climate and Technology: why are the tropics falling behind? *Am. J. Agric. Econ.*, 82:731-737.
- Hamasaki, R; H. Valenzuela and R. Shimabuku. 1999. Bulb onion production in Hawaii, College of Tropical Agriculture and Human Resources, Hawaii, USA.
- Hutton, R. C. and G. J. Wilson. 1986. Onion: Effect of sowing date on maturity, yield and quality of 'Pukekohe Longkeeper' and 'Early Longkeeper'. *New Zealand J. Experimental Agri.*, 14(4):453-457.
- Kelley, W. T. and D. M. Granberry. 2000. Dry bulb onion, commercial vegetable production. The University of Georgia Extension Service Publications Circular 801.
- Khan, M. A. and S. Shanmugasundaram. 2003. Effect of photoperiod on production seed bulb of onion (*Allium cepa* L.). *Bangladesh J. Seed Sci. & Technol.*, 7(1&2):43-43.

- Khan, M. A. and S. Shanmugasundaram. 2013. Effects of day length on bolting and its effects on growth and development of short day onions. *J. Bangladesh Soc. Agric. Sci. Technol.*, 10(3&4):127-130.
- Khokhar, K. M.; N. Kaska; S.I. Hussain; K. M. Qureshi and T. Mahmood .1990. Effect of different sowing dates, direct seed and transplanting of seedling on maturity days, bulb weight and yield in onion cultivars. *Indian J. Agric. Sci.*, 60 (10):668-671.
- Lee, J. T.; H. D. Kim; S. D. Lee and C. H. Ro. 2012. Variability and interrelationship among yield and bulb quality contributing characters in intermediate-day onion. *Acta Hort.*, 969:123-131.
- Lee, J.; I. Ha; H. Kim; S. Choi; S. Lee J. Kang and G. E. Boyhan. 2016. Regional differences in onion bulb quality and nutrient content, and the correlation between bulb characteristics and storage loss. *Hortic. Sci. Technol.*, 34:807-817.
- Mallor, C.; M. Balcells; F. Mallor and E. Sales. 2011. Genetic variation for bulb size, soluble solids content and pungency in the Spanish sweet onion variety Fuentes de Ebro. Response to selection for low pungency. *Plant Breeding*, 130:55-59.
- Mohamedali, G. H. and A. H. Nourai. 1988. Effects of seed source, sowing date and nitrogen nutrition on the seed yield of the white dehydration onion in Sudan. *J. Hort. Sci.*, 63(2):261-264.
- Nikus, O. and F. Mulugeta. 2010. Onion seed production techniques. A Manual for Extension Agents and Seed Producers. FAO-Crop Diversification and Marketing Development Project. Asella, Ethiopia, May 2010, 24p.
- Rabinowitch, H. D. 1985. Onions and Other Edible *Alliums*. In: CRC Handbook of Flowering (Ed. Haley, H. C.). Boca Raton, CRC Press, Vol. 1, p. 398-409.
- Seppelt, R. 2000. Regionalized optimum control problems for agroecosystem management. *Ecol. Model.*, 131:121-132.
- Singh, A. and B. N. Korla. 1991. Effect of transplanting dates and varieties on number of leaves and yield in onion (*Allium cepa* L.). *Veg. Sci.*, 18(1):24-28.
- Singh, A. and B. N. Korla. 1991. Effects of transplanting dates and varieties on number of leaves and yield in onion. *Ves. Sci.*, 18 (1):24-28.
- Singh, J. P.; M. K. Singh and R. D. Singh. 1993. Growth and yield of onion bulb as influenced by date of transplanting, nitrogen and potash fertilization. *Veg. Sci.*, 20(1):14-17.
- Singh, R. S. 1993. Studies on effect of different transplanting dates on growth and yield of onion (*Allium cepa* L.). *Curr. Agri.*, 17(1-2):41-45.
- Tarpage, M. W. V.; O. Neya; A. Rouamba and Z. Tamini. 2011. Effect of the production season of bulbs and the stage of the seed maturity on the physiological characteristics of onion seed (*Allium cepa* L. cv. Violet de Galmi). *J. Animal and Plant Sci.*, 9(2):1169-1178.
- UAAE. 2001. Upper Awash Agro-Industry Enterprise. Progress Report 1996-2002, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.
- Voss, R. E. 1979. Onion production in California. University of California Publication 4097, USA. 49 p.
- Williams, C. L.; M. Liebman; J. W. Edwards; D. E. James; J. W. Singer; R. Arritt and D. Herzmann. 2008. Pattern of regional yield stability in association with regional environmental characteristics. *Crop Sci.*, 48:1545-1559.
- Wright, C. J. and S. Y. Sobeih. 1986. The photoperiodic regulation bulbing in onions (*Allium cepa* L.). I. Effects of irradiance. *J. Hort. Sci.*, 61:331-335.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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